

Air Traffic and Satellite Constraints on Laser Guide Star Operations at Cerro Pachón

Vincent Garrel^a, Aurea Garcia-Rissmann^a, Julian Christou^b, Mario Castro^a, and Carlos Quiroz^a

^aNSF NOIRLab, La Serena, Chile

^bNSF NOIRLab, Tucson, USA

ABSTRACT

The operation of laser guide star systems at astronomical observatories faces increasing challenges from both commercial air traffic and satellite constellations. At Cerro Pachón in Chile, the Gemini South telescope's GeMS multi-conjugate adaptive optics system uses a 22W sodium laser that must comply with both US Space Force protocols for satellite avoidance and Chilean DGAC regulations for aircraft protection. We present statistics on the growing impact of these constraints on observation efficiency, analyze current mitigation strategies including laser declassification efforts and reduced avoidance cones, and propose future solutions. Our analysis shows that air traffic over northern Chile has grown to night-time levels comparable to daytime operations (+15% annual growth), while the number of active LEO satellites increases by approximately 20% annually. These trends necessitate community-wide coordination to maintain observation efficiency while ensuring safety compliance.

Keywords: Laser guide star, air traffic, satellite constellations, adaptive optics, Cerro Pachón, Gemini South

1. INTRODUCTION

The Gemini Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics System (GeMS) at Cerro Pachón operates a 22W sodium laser for creating artificial guide stars. This system must comply with two distinct regulatory frameworks:

- **Chilean DGAC regulations:** These govern aircraft protection, requiring laser shutdown when planes are detected within a 15° avoidance cone.
- **US Space Force protocols:** Managed through the Laser Clearing House at Vandenberg Space Force Base, these regulations prevent laser propagation to satellites, particularly in Low Earth Orbit (LEO). They require submission for targets about one week in advance.

While historically low impact, these 2 regulations have recently significantly affected our observation schedule and efficiency. We introduce first the Chilean situation concerning of airplane avoidance. Then we present the situation concerning the satellites avoidance. We then look at the recent statistical impact these 2 independent factors combined have on operation.

2. AIR TRAFFIC CONSTRAINTS

Due to the particular configuration of Chile with the Andes, The Direction General de Avacion Civil (DGAC) airliner corridor from northern Chilean cities (Arica, Iquique, Calama, Antofagasta, Copiapó) to Santiago passes east of the Gemini South telescope as shown in Fig.1. Commercial airplanes are equipped with transponders

Figure 1. National planes nightly flight maps over northern Chile, Cities are marked. ADS-B records are now captured on the Gemini Observatory rooftop seen on the top right. GSO marks the position of the Gemini South telescope while LCO marks the position of the Las Campanas Observatory where the ELT-class GMT will be built. In the red zoomed area, the observable zone seen by the telescope and where laser propagation can be restricted.

system, which can be detected by 2 of our local antennas (one mounted on the roof, and TBAD the directional antenna)

The current protocol with DGAC requires avoiding laser propagation when aircraft are nearby, using a large (15°) avoidance cone inherited from initial agreements where human spotters identified planes. The Gemini Observatory is now using VITRO, a client software feeding the stream as seen by the DGAC air controllers. With improved safety measures in place, a new agreement could reduce this cone and limit operational impact. VITRO is the practical solution as it allows the operators to pause the observing sequence in advance, without losing the science instrument exposure time.

As a last line of defense, Figure 2 shows the TBAD (Transponder-Based Aircraft Detector) system [3], which activates only on the telescope boresight and automatically shuts down laser propagation when aircraft are detected within the avoidance cone. The system is always active. We here used it to examine all tracks from the telescope when the telescope is observing, with or without laser. The corridor from northern Chile to the capital Santiago is clearly confirmed to be the vast majority of airplanes affecting the laser operation by generating interruptions.

At the time of the writing, an individual plane interrupts about 3 min of operation, while a clump (several planes following each other) are costing up to 10min of operation. This is heavily influenced by the granularity of the science exposure time required by the scientific instrument.

Further author information: (Send correspondence to V.G.)
 V.G.: E-mail: Vincent.Garrel@noirlab.edu

Figure 2. TBAD antenna, the 7 panels structure mounted on the telescope top ring detects the planes in the bore-sight of the AO instruments. The system is wired to shutdown laser propagation when a plane is detected within the avoidance cone. The right plot shows individual plane detection (red) over a semester of pointings (blue).

3. SATELLITE CONSTRAINTS

The US Laser Clearing House protocol prevents laser propagation to satellites, particularly LEO objects. Propagation requests are handled at the Vandenberg Space Force Base for all laser-equipped telescopes on US soil or funded by the National Science Foundation. We have seen a steady increase of the number of interrupts generated over the years with a large increase coinciding with the launch of the internet providing satellites constellations. Currently, satellite owners have no mechanism to opt out of this protection scheme.

The Gemini Observatory holds a SQL database retracing all submitted permissions to propagate. Among those, a set of 57 engineering (altaz coordinates, not season dependent) targets was always submitted. It can be used as a proxy to track the evolution of the number and duration of events where laser propagation is not allowed. Historical data (Figure 4) shows the evolution of window occurrences and associated time losses over recent years. Consecutive nights can display a widely different number of events, the cause is unknown at the time of writing.

The number of active LEO satellites is estimated at 8,400, with a projected increase of 1,700 satellites annually (+20% per year).

4. IMPACT ON RECENT OPERATION

The increasing number of commercial satellites, especially in the frame of satellite constellations affected laser operations by multiplying interruptions. Figure 3 shows a recent example observation windows for real astronomical targets, where orange striped bars indicate propagation interdiction. One of our recent mitigation strategy consisted in postponing laser operation for the night when the numbers of windows were clearly identifier as in the "outlier" population.

Figures 5 and 6 show histograms of air traffic and satellite window crossings per hour over Cerro Pachón. While completely independent in terms of source, their activity statistically peak in the middle of the night between 23h and 00h where it becomes difficult to operate at all. While the satellite windows are known in advance, the airplane positions are not which makes efficient mitigation strategies difficult to implement with the current set of regulation.

5. MITIGATION STRATEGIES

Several approaches could be being pursued at the observatory level to reduce interruptions while maintaining safety:

- **Postpone operation:** Avoid the outlier nights in terms of satellites windows.
- **Redirect operation:** Privilege the targets in the West direction during the peak activity hours.

Figure 3. Example of observation windows for real targets on July 14, 2025. Orange striped bars indicate periods where propagation is prohibited over a given submitted target.

Figure 4. Evolution of window occurrences and associated time losses over recent years, using a baseline of 57 engineering targets. Each dot represents a night. The hypothesis is for a 3 min per single interrupt. If several interrupt events are generated within 3 minutes, the total timing is correctly merged.

- **Reduced avoidance cones:** Negotiations with DGAC to strictly adhere to TBAD and its 15° avoidance cone

Some other can be pursued as a community, for example the recent approach to declassify our lasers. NOIRLab sponsored a workshop in April 2023 to initiate efforts to declassify the 22W laser class now common in ground-based telescopes [2].

Rerouting airplanes by a about 10 kilometers east side would virtually remove the airplanes from our detection range. It could be promoted by our community in the same manner as of the dark skies initiatives.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The growing constraints from air traffic and satellite constellations present significant challenges to laser guide star operations at Cerro Pachón. While mitigation strategies exist, their implementation requires coordinated efforts across the astronomical community and regulatory agencies. The trends of increasing air traffic (+15%

Figure 5. Histogram per hour of airplanes crossing Cerro Pachón’s airspace on the north-to-south route.

Figure 6. Histogram per hour of satellite windows crossing over Cerro Pachón.

annually) and satellite deployments (+20% annually) underscore the urgency of these efforts to preserve the scientific productivity of adaptive optics systems.

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References

- [1] Dirección General de Aeronáutica Civil. “Tráfico aéreo comercial en el país”. In: (2023). Accessed: 2023-11-15. URL: <https://www.dgac.gob.cl/trafico-aereo-comercial-en-el-pais/>.
- [2] NSF NOIRLab. *Workshop on Mitigating Satellite Constellations and Laser Propagation*. Accessed: 2023-05-10. 2023. URL: <https://noirlab.edu/science/events/websites/wmscalp>.
- [3] Paul J. Jr. Stomski, Thomas W. Jr. Murphy, and Randy Campbell. “Recent developments in aircraft protection systems for laser guide star operations”. In: *Proc. SPIE 8447, Adaptive Optics Systems III*. Vol. 8447. 2012, 84474R. DOI: [10.1117/12.926673](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.926673).